

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT COMPOST TYPES ON THE HUMUS CONTENT OF TYPICAL SIEROZEMS SOILS

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Abstract. The study aimed to evaluate the effect of various compost materials on the humus content of typical irrigated sierozem. A laboratory experiment was conducted using nine treatments with four replications, including cotton residues, wheat straw, alfalfa roots, and ephemeral plants. All treatments were incubated for ten months under controlled moisture conditions. Results revealed that composting significantly increased soil humus content compared to the control. The highest increase (1.256%) was recorded in soils amended with ephemeral plant compost, followed by the mixture of cotton residues (1.160%). The results highlight the potential of organic amendments in improving soil fertility and sustaining humus balance in irrigated agroecosystems.

Keywords: humus content, composting, sierozems soils, organic residues, ephemeral plants residue, soil fertility.

Introduction. Soil organic matter, particularly humus, plays a crucial role in maintaining soil fertility, structure, and biological activity. In arid and semi-arid regions, such as Central Asia, the long-term use of irrigation has led to gradual depletion of soil humus, which negatively affects productivity and ecological sustainability. Maintaining humus balance is therefore one of the key challenges in managing irrigated soils.

Composting with plant residues has been recognized as an effective method to restore soil organic matter and improve its chemical and biological properties (1,7). Plant residues differ in their biochemical composition, decomposition rate, and contribution to humification processes. In Uzbekistan, where cotton and wheat are the dominant crops, large amounts of crop residues are produced annually but are often underutilized. Several international studies confirm that humic substances not only improve nutrient retention but also enhance the physical and biological properties of soils [4].

The present study was conducted to determine how different types of compost materials—derived from cotton, alfalfa, wheat, and ephemeral plants—affect the humus content of typical irrigated gray soils. The findings contribute to

the development of sustainable organic management strategies for improving soil fertility in the arid agroecosystems of Central Asia.

Material and methods. The laboratory experiment was conducted on typical sierozems soils collected from long-irrigated fields in the Uzbekistan. The experimental design included nine treatments with four replications each:

1. Soil (control)
2. Soil + cotton leaves
3. Soil + cotton roots
4. Soil + cotton stems
5. Soil + cotton leaves + roots
6. Soil + all cotton residues (leaves + roots + stems)
7. Soil + alfalfa roots
8. Soil + wheat straw
9. Soil + ephemeral plants

Each sample was placed in 3 kg plastic pots and incubated for ten months under controlled moisture (50–60% of field capacity). Compost materials were finely shredded and thoroughly mixed with soil before incubation. The analysis of humus fractions followed the Tyurin method, determining humic and fulvic acids, total organic carbon (Corg), and their ratios [8,9]. Scientific sources were used to analyze the results [3]. Data were statistically analyzed using Microsoft Excel and the methodology proposed by Dospexov (1985) [5].

Results and Discussion. The results demonstrated that the humus content of typical irrigated gray soils changed significantly under the influence of different composts (Table 1).

Nº	Experimental variants	Spring (start)	Autumn (end)
1	Soil (control)	1.110	1.100
2	Soil + cotton leaves	1.110	1.129
3	Soil + cotton roots	1.110	1.119
4	Soil + cotton stems	1.110	1.127
5	Soil + cotton leaves + roots	1.110	1.136
6	Soil + all cotton residues (leaves + roots + stems)	1.110	1.160
7	Soil + alfalfa roots	1.110	1.147
8	Soil + wheat straw	1.110	1.139
9	Soil + ephemeral plants	1.110	1.256

At the beginning of the experiment, the humus content of all variants was identical (1.110%), indicating homogeneous initial conditions. After ten months of incubation, notable differences appeared between treatments. The control soil showed a slight decrease to 1.100%, reflecting natural mineralization and humus depletion in the absence of organic input.

In contrast, all compost-treated soils exhibited an increase in humus content. The most significant rise occurred in the ephemeral plant compost treatment, reaching 1.256%, which represents a 0,146% increase relative to the control. The mixture of all cotton residues also produced a considerable effect (1.160%), followed by alfalfa roots (1.147%) and wheat straw (1.139%). The individual cotton residues (leaves, roots, or stems alone) provided modest but consistent increases (1.119–1.129%).

These differences are primarily related to the biochemical composition of the added residues. Ephemeral plants contain easily decomposable organic compounds and have a relatively balanced carbon-to-nitrogen ratio, facilitating faster mineralization and humus formation. Cotton residues, although richer in lignin, contribute to more stable humus fractions over time. Alfalfa roots, being a legume, add biologically fixed nitrogen that promotes microbial activity and humification.

The findings align with previous studies (6, 2), which reported that composting with diverse organic sources improves soil organic matter content and structure. The data suggest that combining various plant residues enhances both the quantity and quality of humus due to complementary decomposition dynamics.

5. Conclusion. Composting with plant residues significantly increased the humus content of typical irrigated soils. The highest humus accumulation was recorded in the soil with ephemeral plant compost (1.256%), followed by the mixture of all cotton residues (1.160%). Regular incorporation of organic residues into irrigated soils prevents humus depletion and improves soil fertility and sustainability. The use of locally available crop residues is an environmentally friendly and cost-effective method to maintain soil productivity in Central Asian agroecosystems.

References:

1. Anderson, D.W., & Schoenau, J.J. (2017). Soil Humus Fractions. In Encyclopedia of Soils in the Environment. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-409547-2.12345-6>

2. Ampong, E.E., et al. (2022). Understanding the Role of Humic Acids on Crop Performance and Soil Health. *Frontiers in Agronomy*, 4, 848621. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fagro.2022.848621>
3. Аринушкина, Е.В. (1970). Руководство по химическому анализу почв. Москва: Издательство МГУ. – 487 с.
4. Becher, M., et al. (2022). Fractional Composition of Organic Matter and Properties of Humic Fractions in Soils. *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, 23(3), 208–222. <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/150365>
5. Доспехов, Б.А. (1979). Методика полевого опыта (с основами статистической обработки результатов исследований). Москва: Колос. – 416 с.
6. García, C., Hernández, T., et al. (2016). Structure–Property–Function Relationship in Humic Fractions from Soils and Composted Materials. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 20798. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep20798>
7. Olk, D.C., Marcel, H., et al. (2019). Environmental and Agricultural Relevance of Humic Fractions and Their Extraction. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 48(4), 965–979. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2019.02.0041>
8. Пономарева, В.В., & Плотникова, Т.А. (1980). Гумус и почвообразование. Ленинград: Наука. – 234 с.
9. Тюрин И.В. Органическое вещество почв. – М.: Наука, 1972. – 342 с.

